
History of Tribal's Protest against Turga Pump Storage Hydraulic Power Project of Ajodhya Pahar, Purulia, West Bengal, India: An Environmental Movement

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ABSTRACT

Ajodhya hill is a small mountain range of Purulia district, west Bengal, India. It is an extended part of Eastern Ghat Mountain with its historical, mythological and ecological value. The Santal tribes have resided here since immemorial. The hill became in a spot light when the West Bengal govt. started a pump storage hydraulic electricity project in 2002. The 900 MW Purulia Pump Storage Project (P.P.S.P) was executed by west Bengal state electricity distribution company limited (W.B.S.E.D.C.L) with the financially help of Japan International co-operation agency (J.I.C.A). After successfully running the Purulia pump storage hydraulic power project at Ajodhya pahar (hill), the West Bengal govt. announced another hydraulic project in the same place in 2015 under the name 'Turga Pump Storage Hydraulic Electricity Project'. After the announcement of the project the local tribal people raise their voice against the project. They want to keep the environment on the hill. The present paper focuses on the tribal movement against the Turga Project at Ajodhya hill, Purulia, West Bengal.

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INTRODUCTION: Purulia is a district of west Bengal, India with its rich cultural, historical and ecological value. Generally the district is tribal infested. Ajodhya pahar (a small mountain range), an

extended part of Eastern Ghat mountain, is situated at Bagmundi block of Purulia district. The area belongs to the Chhotanagpur plateau. Ajodhya pahar (hill) has its own historical, mythological and ecological perspective. It is a late Pleistocene microlithic site in the eastern part of India. Several Paleolithic and Mesolithic stone tools were discovered here [1]. According to Indian mythology, the lord Rama and Sita had come to Ajodhya hill and stayed here during their exile. Sita gets thirsty and Rama throws an arrow towards the earth soil and water come out, and Sita drinks the water. The place is known as Sita –Kunda [2]. Various flora and fauna are cited here. So many medicinal plants found on the Ajodhya pahar like Mushkdana, Kalmegh, Neem, Palash, Haritaki, Amlaki, Kuruchi etc. Large shade tree jungle found here. It is an elephant corridor of Dalma range. There are 85 villages in Ajodhya, and total population, as per the 2011 census is 1600. Basically most of the total population belongs to tribal Santal community. Their basic occupations are hunting, collecting wood from jungle, making bidi (cigarettes made by leaves), collecting fruits, animal husbandry and somewhere cultivation [3]. At a time, the area is not so much popular because of the moist activity upon the hill. But the area became a spot light when the West Bengal govt. started a pump storage hydraulic electricity project in 2002. The 900 MW ‘Purulia Pump Storage Project’ (P.P.S.P) was executed by West Bengal state electricity distribution company limited (W.B.S.E.D.C.L) with the financial help of ‘Japan International Co-operation Agency’ (J.I.C.A). The project started in 2002 and was completed in 2008. Now it is commercially run [4]. The area became a picnic spot for this project. A pump storage hydraulic power project is different from a normal hydraulic power project. In a pump storage project, two water reservoirs made in two different levels, one in high and one in low. A water conductor system will connect two reservoirs through an underground power house. Power will be generated when water passing through upper reservoir to lower reservoir, with turbines installed in lower reservoir. Water is then supplied from lower to upper reservoir by pump. Electricity is produced by cyclic use of water stream [5]. Now this type of hydraulic project is very popular throughout the world because it preserves the water in reservoirs and allows continuous use of the water by pump. After successfully running of the Purulia pump storage hydraulic power project at Ajodhya pahar, the West Bengal govt. announced another hydraulic project in the same place in 2015 under the name ‘Turga Pump Storage Hydraulic Electricity Project’ (T.P.S.P). After announcement of the project, the local tribal people raised their voice against the project. They want to keep the environment on Ajodhya hill. In previous project the govt. gave some fake promises to the tribals like free electricity, jobs etc. About 3 lakh trees cut down for the previous project. Govt. officials promised to plant 3 lakhs trees in another place. But the officials cannot take any plantation programme. The tribals are mostly dependent on the forest on the hill. They organised themselves in various groups

and protested against the Turga project in the name of saving the environment on the hill. Some intellectuals of the district and some outsiders are also involved in the movement. From the very first day of the announcements of the Turga project, tribal are raised their voice against the project. They formed 'Ajodhya Buru Bachao Samiti Mancha' and started campaigning against the project. Wall campaigning against the project also started. They gave a deputation to district magistrate of Purulia in 2019. They also filed a petition in Calcutta High Court against the Turga project on the basis of violating the 'Forest Right Act' of 2006. The Calcutta High Court gave a temporary stay order on this project. India saw so many environment movements like Chipko movement, Bishnoi movement, Silent valley movement, Narmada bachao movement etc., but the tribal voice of Ajodhya against the Turga project stayed in the dark from an all India perspective. The present paper focuses on tribal's agitation against Turga Pump Storage Hydraulic Electricity Project of Ajodhya hill in Purulia, West Bengal.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY: The objectives of the study are to know-1) what is the Turga pump storage hydro electric project of Ajodhya, Purulia? 2) Historicity of tribal agitation against the Turga pump storage hydro electric project of Ajodhya, Purulia.

STUDY AREA: Area of the study is Ajodhya hill in Purulia District, West Bengal, India.

METHODOLOGY: To do the study, various primary and secondary sources were used. Primary data was collected through an oral interview with the people of the study area. Secondary data was collected from books, articles, internet sources, and news paper reports. Historical method and field observational method used to do the study.

HISTROY OF HYDRAULIC POWER PROJETS OF AJODHYA HILL,

PURULIA: In 1979 Central Electric Authority (C.E.A), a body of the Govt. of India prepared a project on hydraulic power project at Ajodhya pahar, Purulia, West Bengal, with the help of the 'West Bengal State Electricity Board'. They are very much hoping to set up hydro projects here. They found four water streams and possibly set up projects at Kistobazar nala, Turga nala, Kathaljal nala and Bandu nala in Ajodhya. Investigation is done separately by the West Bengal State Electricity Board, a body of the Govt. of West Bengal. Now the West Bengal State Electricity Board converted to 'West Bengal State Electricity Distribution Company Limited' (W.B.S.E.D.C.L). On the Kistobazar nala of the Bamni River, the Purulia Pump Storage Project (P.P.S.P) was built up. The 900 MW Purulia Pump Storage Project was sanctioned by Govt. of India in February 1994 with the financial help of the 'Japan

International Co-operation Agency' (J.I.C.A). A loan agreement was also signed. 'Electric Power Development Company' (E.P.D.C) of Japan and WAPCOS of India consulted on the whole project. Purulia Pump Storage Project executed by W.B.S.E.D.C.L with the financial help of J.I.C.A. The project starts in 2002, is completed on 2008. The project was inaugurated by contemporary Chief Minister Mr. Buddhadeb Bhattacharjee. It is now commercially run [6]. In a pump storage project two water reservoir were made at two different levels, one high and one low. A water conductor system will connect two reservoirs through an underground power house. Power will be generated when water passes from the upper reservoir to the lower reservoir, with turbines and generators installed in the lower reservoir. Water is then supplied from lower to upper reservoir by a pump. Electricity produced by cyclic use of water streams [7]. Near about 3lakh trees cut down and a large forest land devastated to build up the project. After successfully running of Purulia Pump Storage Project, the govt. of West Bengal wants to set up four hydraulic projects on Ajodhya pahar. Turga Project is next proposed project on Turga nala, a tributary of Subarnarekha.

Lower reservoir (lower dam) of P.P.S.P

Upper reservoir (upper dam) of P.P.S.P

HISTROY OF PROPOSED TURGA PUMP STORAGE HYDRO ELECTRICITY

PROJECT OF AJODHYA, PURULIA: As we mentioned earlier, in 1979, the 'Central Electric Authority' (C.E.A), a body of the Govt. of India prepared a project on hydraulic power projects at Ajodhya pahar, Purulia, West Bengal. They found four water streams and possibly set up project at Kistobazar nala, Turga nala, Kathaljal nala and Bandu nala of Ajodhya. On the Kistobazar nala of the Bamni River, the Purulia Pump Storage Project (P.P.S.P) was built up. After successfully running of Purulia Pump Storage Project, the govt. of West Bengal wants to set up Turga Pump Storage Hydro Electricity Project on Turga nala, a tributary of the Subarnarekha River. The Central Electricity Authority (C.E.A) gave a conditional clearance of 1000mw (250*4) Turga Pump Storage Hydraulic

Power Project in Purulia of West Bengal in 2016. The total estimated cost of the project is Rs. 4500 cr. C.E.A chairman of that time Mr. S.D. Dubey, stated that they had cleared the project, now it only needs environment clearance. State power minister of West Bengal Govt. Mr. Sobhandeb Chatterjee cleared that the formal letter has not arrived from C.E.A. He also stated that the govt. wants to feed the hydraulic project with 1200 MW solar power [8]. Central Electricity Authority sent the formal letter to the office of W.B.S.E.D.C.L in October 2016. Now the project needs clearance from the state forest department because the maximum land for the project is the state forest dept's land [9]. The Turga Pump Storage Project focused on utilization of rainfall in the Turga nala of Ajodhya hill. In this project an upper dam and a lower dam across Turga nala will be constructed. Four Reversible Pump-Turbine installed in underground power house, which have a 250 MW generating capacity. The areas of the proposed upper dam are 23°12'47"N and 86°04'20"E and lower dam are 23°11'49" and 86°04'13"E. The topographical sheet no for the project is 731/4/NW of the survey of India. The environmental clearance from the govt. of India for the project Vide No. J-12011/13/2013-IA.I(R) dated 02.07.2018. The total land required for the project is 292.0 hector of which 234.0 hector are forest land [10]. WAPCOS, a body of the govt. of India, was appointed as local consultant for the project. J.POWER of Japan is chief consultant for the Project. The two companies do all the plans, projects and tenders. W.B.S.E.D.C.L executed body of the project. Central Electricity Authority and Central Water Commission will join in all work of the project. Solar energy will be used for the project [11]. A loan agreement signed on 2nd November, 2018 for the project in New Delhi. The agreement signed between Sri C.S. Mohapatra, Additional Secretary, Department of Economic Affairs, and the Ministry of Finance, Govt. of India, and Mr. Katsou Matsumoto, Chief Representative of Japan International Co-operation Agency (J.I.C.A) [12]. The Turga Project started in October 2016. The Central Electricity Authority approved the project in same time. Land acquisition was completed in February 2017. The Project received cabinet approval of the West Bengal Govt. in May 2017. The project got forest clearance in 2018 in the month of July [13].

TRIBAL AGITATION AGAINST TURGA PUMP STORAGE HYDRAULIC

PROJECT: When W.B.S.E.D.C.L started construction work on Turga nala, tribal people raised their voice against the project. They organised themselves and started campaign against the project. All the villagers near the Turga nala or other part of the hill started protesting against the project. Some outsiders also joined with them. Kolkata based Sourav Mukherjee, Suman Mandal and Kaushik Mukherjee actively participated in the movement. All are environment activists. Sourav mukherjee,

Officials of W.B Govt. and W.B.S.E.D.C.L Signed an agreement with the officials of J.POWER (Japan), Source: W.B.S.E.D.C.L

Kistobazar Nala Pumped Storage or PPS, the first project and Turga Falls, where the second Pumped Storage Project is already planned.

Project area of P.P.S.P and proposed area of Turga Project. (Source: countercurrent.org)

who call himself as Sourav Pakritibadi, is an alumini of Presidency University. He was a student of zoology of the Presidency University. Both Sourav Mukherjee and Suman Mandal is school teacher. Kaushik Mukherjee is a former student of Jadavpur University. From the very first day of the agitation they have been involved in it. All were involving in aware the tribal people of the hill against the project. They also wrote articles to aware the civil society about the tribal agitation [14]. Tribes of Ajodhya formed ‘Ajodhya Buru Bachao Andolon Samhiti Mancha’. As we know, the hill has a vast forest, and the tribes and others species totally depend on the forest. If the project is set up, then thousand of animals and humans will be displaced who are dependent on it. Actually, the agitation came from the bad experience of previous Purulia Pump Storage Project. It is set up on the Bamni river Stream. Villagers near P.P.S.P stated that State govt. promises them free electricity and Jobs for those who residing around 5km radius of P.P.S.P, but govt. cannot keep the promises. At a time those who are depended on the Bamni River stream now they faced immense problem. Villagers cannot fetch water from tube wells in the summer because ground level water is very low now because the whole river stream goes into the dams. They have to collect waters from wells. An interview with Sagun Tudu on 11.4.2019, resided near P.P.S.P, he expressed his bitter experience about the project. He said that at “at a time the area is covered with full of green and there is no problem of water. Now the area has become dry. “Amra ki bhabe bachbo, bolte paren? (How do we live?)”[15].The nearby villagers can’t get water for their cultivated land. If the Turga Project or proposed other projects set up then the total bio-diversity of the hill will be destroyed. Tribes are fear of that. An estimated 292 hector land of forest would be

required for the Turga Project. Leopard, Jungle Cat, Leopard Cat, Wolf, Hyena, Jackal, Fox, Black Bear, Wild Pig, Common otter, Langur etc lived in the jungle. Where they go, tribes asked. Ajodhya is habitat and corridor of elephants. If the projects set up, they will enter the locality. Destroy the buildings and corps. An elephant died by high extension wire recently. Deforestation and other construction activity on Ajodhya hill increased the risk of Soil erosion and landslides. Ranga, Tarpana, Teliabhasa, Hatitadra, Barlehar villages will be destroyed if the projects done [16]. The total estimated land of four projects is 1200 hectars and probably 12, 00,000 trees have been lost. P.P.S.P already consumed 3lakh tree and seven hills. Tribes are totally depended on their hill and jungle. Why they are giving up their rights over it? Sunita Mandi of Bandhgutu village stated that they all became beggars if the entire firm land taken for the construction. Once, the area was full of granaries but now it is barren. An interview with Bura Mandi of Tarapana village near the proposed area of Turga Project on 11.04.2019, he expressed his deep concern about their livelihood and life. He stated that they cannot give up their rights over jal (water), jami (land), jungle (forest), pahar (hill). The upper dam of P.P.S.P became a picnic spot now. The use of plastic and thermo cal creates problems of nearby villagers. The area has become a heap of garbage now. Villagers lost 40-50 cattle when they ate plastic. The proposed area of Turga Project is also connected with tribe's spiritual sentiment. They demanded for their land remains free in any condition. At a time it is very difficult to find sun light at Ajodhya hill, because it is full with green, but now it become open because thousand of trees have been cut down. They demanded for their holy land 'Sutandih' (where they meet and celebrate) and 'Marang Buru hill' (Sacred grove of the tribes). If the Turga Project build up the hill will be cut down [17].

In the early days of the movement, tribes held small meetings in the hill region and organised rallies at Bagmundi block area to aware the tribes and civil society against the Turga project. Tribes showed placards against the project. They made wall graffiti's against the project. They formed 'Ajodhya Buru Bachao Samhati Mancha'. Two social organization of the tribes 'Bharat jakat Majhi Pargana Mahal' and 'Bharat Jakat Majhi Juyan Pargana Mahal' adjoined in the agitation. The two organisations always fight for the rights of the tribes. Slowly the movement became a mass movement. The two Social organizations 'Bharat Jakat Majhi Pargana Mahal' and 'Bharat Jakat Majhi Juyan Pargana Mahal' organised a mass convention in the front of Purulia District Magistrate office on 25.06.2019. Many tribes from the district join in the convention. They with their traditional arms and musical instruments (like Dhamsa, Madal), joined in the convention. They gave a deputation to the District Magistrate. They wanted total withdraw of the Turga project. They want to save their right over jal (water), jami (land),

jungle (forest), pahar (hill). Ratan Tudu, President of ‘Bharat Jakat Majhi Pargana Mahal’ stated that no project build up to destroy the life of the tribes. When govt. set up P.P.S.P, it promised the tribes that 3lakh trees would be planted in other land but govt. cannot keep that promise. They also promised to get free electricity but it has not been fulfilled [18].

(Two tribal lady showing placards against the Turga Porject, Source: Face book wall of Sourabh Pakritibadi and Suman Mandal)

Suman Mandal, an active leader of the movement, raised a good question on the projects that the P.P.S.P and Turga are located at a distance of 2.5 to 3km from each other. How is it possible to save the area from natural disaster if the project is set up? The Forest Department planted Eucalyptus trees in the name of the plantation. These trees absorbed more and more water. It causes the water crisis in the hill. 20,000 people may be displaced if the all projects implemented, he said [19]. Sagar Chakraborty, range officer of Ajodhya, can't speak on this matter, but he said a joint forest management committee has been formed in this issue. According to forest department of Purulia there are 580 types of birds and 486 types' animals living in the region. Where they are going if the project is implemented? D.F.O of Purulia M.R. Ramaprasad Badna stated that they did not know how many trees there but Wild life conservation plan formed there [20]. On the eve of the 2019 Loksabha Election the walls of Ajodhya were filled with the campaign against the Turga project, not the voting campaign of any political party. A notable political party of India also used the tribal agitation against the govt. in its vote campaign [21]. The ‘Ajodhaya Buru Bachao Samhati Mancha’ had also organised a mass convention in Kolkata to assembles villagers from Ajodhya, Peoples of Purulia, environment activists, and civil society members to highlighted the movement from Bengal as well as all India perspective . The tribes are can't want to destroy the nature in the name of development. A School teacher, Supen Hembram said that if they get job they will retire in 60, but if they save forest it will give them generations to livelihood. He also stated that why govt. should not focus on education and health which are in poor condition in the hill, what types of developments govt. wants makehere? [22]. Kaushik Chakraborty, a former student of Jadavpur University, also a leader of the movement made a documentary and demonstrated it in five villages. The

name of the documentary is 'Banmanush' (jungle man). The police of Arsha Police Station arrested Kaushik Chakraborty and his companion Iman Santra, a primary school teacher of Hooghly. When they were going to rail station to take train to Kolkata from Purulia, police arrested them. Police officials of Arsha Police Station stated that they are roaming suspiciously in the villages so they were arrested but some time later they were freed. District Police official stated the same. But it is not true, Kaushik Chakraborty Made this documentary against the govt. and Turga project [23].

In spite of all these the 'Ajodhya Buru Bachao Samhati Mancha' filled a petition in Calcutta High Court against the project. Sushil Murmu, a villager of Ranga village filled the petition that the project violated the 'Forest Right Act' of 2006, which mandates a resolution from Gram Sabhas is needed before implementing any project. According to F.R.A, if forest land has to be acquired then at least 50% of the population dependent on the land has to give consent in Gram Sabhas and a third of the villagers have to be women. There are two Gram Panchayet at the hill area- Ajodhya Gram Panchayet and Bagmundi Gram Panchayet. Ajodhya Gram Panchayet has no signature and Bagmundi Panchayet has only 24 signatures on the govt. resolution but total population of the hill is 1600 as per the 2011 census. The case no is W.P. 20576(w) of 2018, Rabi Besra & ors. VS, state of West Bengal. Santanu Chakraborty is villager's lawyer. During the hearing at the Court how administration official of Purulia district has issued a false and fabricated certificate that claims all procedures have been followed for conducting Gram Sabhas, to have the majority (50%) consent about the project including the settlement of rights of the affected villagers under the project. On 2nd, 2019 July the Calcutta High Court ordered a temporary stay on the Turga Project till August 31, 2019 while hearing the plea [24]. State govt. goes to the division bench to challenge the order. Now the Projects and tribes fate depend on the further Court order but tribes still continue the movement.

(Don't want, don't want, don't want Turga Project) (Our environment, our life, equal to mother)

(Save the green Ajodhya)

(Don't destroy our peaceful life)

(Jungle is our father-Mother, don't make us orphan) (Don't destroy the environment of Ajodhya)

THE WALL GRAFFITIS AT AJODHYA HILL AGAINST TURGA PROJECT(Source: PURULIA-purulia facebook page)

TURGA PROJECT MOVEMENT AS AN ENVIRONMENT MOVEMENT: An environmental movement can be defined as a social or political movement , for the conservation of environment or for the improvement of environment. The environmental movements favor the sustainable management of natural resources. The term ‘ environment movement’ used to describe regional conflicts and struggles of livelihood issues and to save ecology for livelihood. Environment movement is a type of social movement that involves an array of individuals, groups and conditions that perceive a common interest in environment protection and act to bring about close eyes in environment policies and practicies [25]. In history of India we saw several environment movements to save the ecology and involvement of tribes in those movements. Major reason behind the movements are control nover natural resouces, false government development policies, socio econmic reasons and environmental destruction.Tribes are basically depend on environment because their livelihood depend on it. They have lived with the nature since time immerorial. Turga Project movement of Ajodhya is one such movement where tribes want to save their right over jal(water), jami(land), jungel(forest) and pahar(hill). They clearly rejected the govt. theory of development and jobs and others compensesions. They only try to save the ecology of Ajodhya hill.

(Mass deputation to D.F.O Purulia)

Source: Sambad Pratidin Patrika

(Meeting of tribes against the project)

Source: countercurrents.org

CONCLUSION: India is a developing country. Nation need more more electric energy for socalled development, industrial and household purpose. In the age of modern nation states and liberal economic governments, they also focus on corporates and give them power to rules over the natural resources. State forces its all machinary to set up these projects in the name of development. Where the peoples go who are dependent on the nature? Tribes has a long history of conservation of ecology, for not to uses it but they love ecology and they want to save it. Purulia is a drought prone district of west bengal but a time it is not so much draught prone. In colonial period british govt. cut millions of trees here for ship building, making railway track sleeper and other purposes. If govt. want to cut more and more trees it devastated the total ecology of Purulia and it hampers on total rain fall of the district. As we all know, the govt. has tried in many ways to implement the projects at Ajodhya hill. Perhaps govt. will succeed in implementing of all the projects on the lives of the tribes at Ajodhya but tribal’s voice can to be resist. Recently Purulia saw many environment movent like ‘Pahar bachao movement’ of Dhanardih village of Kashipur, ‘Pahar bachao movment’ of Senera and Bero village of Raghunathpur, ‘Jungle bachao movement’ of Kotshila. Not only the tribes but also general civilians also involve on those movements. The tribes of Ajodhya threatened the govt. if they are not stop all the projects govt. will see another ‘hul’(Santal revolt).

REFERANCES

1. Dey, G & Dey, S(2010): Bharat Barsher Itihas(Pragoitihask jug theke adi madhya jug), Poggressive Publisher, Kolkata, pp. 169-170
2. [https://en.m.wikipedia.org>wiki>Ajodhya Hills.](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ajodhya_Hills)

3. <https://WWW.Onefive.com>>Purulia>Ajodhya
4. <https://WWW.WBSEDCL/PPSP>
5. [https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pump Storage Hydel Electricity Project](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pump_Storage_Hydel_Electricity_Project).
6. Banerjee, S (2019): Purulia: Ravaging Ajodhya (or Ayodhya) Hills and Strangulating the Hill-Streams-A forty-years' story accelerating towards fruition, retrived from <https://countercurrents.org>
7. [https://energystorage.org/pumped storage hydro electricity project](https://energystorage.org/pumped_storage_hydro_electricity_project).
8. Electricity body nod for 1000MW Turga hydel project, The Hindu, 20th August, 2016.
9. Turga Prakarper Janno Chai Forest Departmenter Charpatra, The Anandabazar Patrika, 30th October, 2016.
10. <https://WWW.WBSEDCL.in/docs/TPSP>
11. Bandhopadhyay, P (2015, July 11): Turga Prakalpe Paramarso Debe Rashtryata Sangstha, The Anandabazar Patrika.
12. Press information bureau, Govt. of India, Ministry of finance, 2nd November, 2018, New Delhi.
13. Turga Pump Storage Hydroelectric Project, Energybussiness, <https://WWW.energybussiness.com>
14. Mukherjee, K & Sourav (2019): Devastating Developments In Ayodhaya hills, 2nd March, 2019, retrived from <https://sandrp.in>
15. Tudu, S, Personal communication, 11th Aril, 2019.
16. Op. cited, Mukherjee, K & Sourav
17. Singh, G (2020): West Bengal: Ajodhya Hills Alive With Sound Of Resistance By Santal Tribe, 11th May, retrived from <https://WWW.focusmagazine.in>
18. Ibid
19. A report published in the Ei Samay Patrika, 26th June, 2019.
20. Singh, G (2020): West Bengal: Ajodhya Hills Alive With Sound Of Resistance By Santal Tribe, 11th May, retrived from <https://WWW.focusmagazine.in>

21. High Courte Dhakka Khelo Puruliar Turga Prakalpa, Fer Anumatio Nite Hbe Rajyake, The Sambad Pratidin, 20th March, 2019.
22. Chakraborty, S (2019): Ajodhya villagers, forest dwellers stop Bengal govt project at court for now, 10th July, retrived from <https://WWW.downtoearth.org.in>
23. Biswas, S (2019, September 10): Turga Prakalper Birodhitai Tathyachitra Padarshan, Policer Jale Nirmata Saha 2, The Sambad Pratidin.
24. Biswas, M (2019, June 18): Land Acuisition for Turga Storage Project in West Bengaal Violates FRA, Land Conflict Watch, <https://WWW.landconflictwatch.org>
25. Yanki, T (2005): Environmental movement in trasitional socities: A comparartive study on Taiwan and China, comparative politics, vol 37, no2, pp 167-188,